

Job performance of human resource management graduates from the employers' and graduates' perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Graduates' job performance reflects their academic orientation in pursuit of their degrees. Thus, academic institutions should prepare students to be competitive, match the needs of the industry, and become worthy of employment after graduation. This research determines the job performance of human resource management (HRM) graduates in terms of their job competencies, career skills, and team performance from the perception of the graduates and their employers. A quantitative research method with statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Mann-Whitney U Test was used. Findings revealed a significant difference in the respondents' perception, specifically in conveying ideas, use of IT, values, quality work, communication skills, human relations, technical, research, leadership skills, and team performance. The result also shows that graduates perceived themselves as excellent performers, which is in contrast to their employers' perceptions of them as good performers only regarding their job competencies, career skills, and team performance. The differences in perceptions of the performance of the graduates depicts a mismatch between the academe and the industry requirements that result in a recommendation of thorough review and revision of the HRM curriculum, the teaching methodology, and the strategy of the academic institutions to meet the needs of the industry.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Academic institutions are one of the avenues for producing and developing competent human resource (HR) professionals, and their significant role is to produce quality graduates who can meet the needs of different industries. On the other hand, business firms demanded an effective workforce and performers with new competencies to face the ever-changing environment of the industrial revolution 4.0. Furthermore, the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) and many researchers revealed that most employers prefer to recruit graduates with "employability skills" that make graduates more likely to gain employment [1]. However, according to the updated Philippine development plan 2017-2022, it was identified that one of the reasons for the low performance of higher education institutions (HEIs) is its lack of collaboration with industry partners, which contributed to the mismatch between skills taught in schools and labor market requirements. In addition, research by Celis *et al.* [2] observed that the curriculum in the education system is not appropriate for providing graduates with employment opportunities. It was also noted

that of the one million college graduates annually, only 5 to 10% were employed in jobs consistent with their course, and only 30 to 40% found any employment, which resulted in producing unemployed or underemployed graduates. The disturbing situation of unemployment implies the impression that graduates are not yet ready after graduation [3], reflecting their competency preparation during their education in an academic institution. However, they must develop competitive competencies to be at par with others. With this, HEIs worldwide are seeking new business curriculum designs that target the needs of contemporary teaching and learning as well as the competencies and protocols of workplaces [4], which are more structured, systematic, deliberate, and evidence-based processes that recognize graduate employability as the goal of the university alongside teaching, research, and community service [5].

The objective of this study aimed to examine the job performance of the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Management (HRM) of the College of Business, Accountancy, and Public Administration of the Isabela State University along the parameters: i) job competencies; ii) career skills; and iii) team performance as perceived by the graduates and their employers. The key purpose is to analyze the significant difference in the respondents' perceptions to determine if there is a gap between the industry and the academe. The findings of this study will benefit the academic institutions offering HRM degree courses as a basis for reviewing and revising their curriculum, teaching methodology, and strategy, which is mandated and monitored by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Moreover, this study will also prepare academic institutions to achieve sustainable development goal 4 to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Addressing the mismatch between the academe and the industry will produce quality graduates that qualify for employment competency needs and labor market requirements.

2. METHOD

A quantitative research approach was employed to determine the job performance of the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration-Human Resource Management (BSBA-HRM) of the Isabela State University-College of Business, Accountancy, and Public Administration. A sample size of 182 graduates was randomly chosen using Cochran's formula from a total population of 343 graduates from the academic year 2018-2019 to 2022-2023. On the other hand, 43 companies where the graduates were employed were identified as willing to answer the survey questionnaire. Thus, 43 immediate supervisors or employers were purposively chosen to validate the graduates' job performance regarding their job competencies, career skills, and team performance. Moreover, a survey questionnaire was adopted and modified from the study Hinchliffe and Jolly [6] and Garbutt *et al.* [7]. The survey questionnaire was in a Google Form and distributed through social media. A 4-point Likert scale with 1.00, described as poor and 4.00 as excellent, was used in the survey questionnaire.

Furthermore, the data collected were tabulated and analyzed through the SPSS using frequencies and percentages to determine the profile of the two respondents. Weighted mean was used to determine the perception of the graduates and the employers on the job performance of the HRM graduates. Moreover, the Mann-Whitney U Test at .05 significance level was used to determine the significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents because the two independent groups were not normally distributed [8]. With a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .70 and higher, the scale in the survey questionnaire category has good internal consistency, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Internal consistency reliability test

Job performance of HRM graduates	Cronbach's alpha	No. of items
Job competencies	.969	13
Career skills	.976	13
Team performance	.875	5

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Profile of the graduate-respondents

The graduate-respondents' employment profile is shown in Table 2. Regarding the job status of employment, it was worth noting that most graduate respondents have tenured status; however, though they were tenured, most were still in lower positions and had not yet been promoted to higher positions. Also, most of them work in a company for less than a year to two years in service.

Table 2. Profile of the BSBA-HRM graduates

Graduates profile		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Job status	Regular	107	58.79
	Temporary	16	8.79
	Contractual	24	13.19
	Job order/casual	35	19.23
	Total	182	100
Job position	Middle managers	37	20.32
	First-line managers	40	21.98
	Rank and file	105	57.69
	Total	182	100
Number of years in the company	Below 1 year	44	24.4
	1-2 years	120	65.9
	3-4 years	18	9.9
	Total	182	100

3.2. Profile of the employer-respondents

The profile of the employer-respondents is shown in Table 3. As to the type of industry, most of the employers belong to the service industries, followed by employers from the finance or banking industries, and lastly, few were in the government agencies. These employers were asked relevant questions about the graduates' job performance regarding their job competencies, career skills, and team performance. Most employer respondents were first-line managers who directly supervised the graduate respondents. Indeed, their assessment of the graduates' job performance is essential and substantial to feedback.

Table 3. Profile of the employers of the BSBA-HRM graduates

Employers profile		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Type of industry	Government agencies	6	14
	Finance/banking	16	37.2
	Service	21	48.8
	Total	43	100
Level of managerial positions	Top managers	5	11.6
	Middle managers	12	27.9
	First-line managers	25	58.1
	Total	43	100

3.3. Graduates' job performance

The perception of the graduates and the employer's assessment of the job performance of the HRM graduates in terms of job competencies, career skills, and team performance was shown in Tables 4-6 and determined using the weighted mean. On the other hand, the significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents was determined using the Mann-Whitney U Test because the two independent groups were not normally distributed. The data in Table 4 revealed that there is a significant difference in the perception of the graduates and the employers when graduates convey ideas clearly both orally and written in English ($Z=3.400$, $p<.05$) when demonstrating the values of fairness, transparency, accountability, hard work, honesty, patience, diligence, innovativeness, and risk-taking ($Z=2.228$, $p<.05$), apply the principles of the different forms of communications ($Z=2.063$, $p<.05$), develop the ability to access, retrieve, and disseminate information using IT ($Z=2.034$, $p<.05$), perform quality work ($Z=2.377$, $p<.05$), develop a wholesome personality ($Z=4.012$, $p<.0$), and participate in environmental scanning/awareness ($Z=2.912$, $p<.05$). The result indicates a significant difference between the graduate's perception of being competent and the assessment of the employer on their job competency performance among those constructs.

Moreover, Table 4 also compares the perceptions of graduates and employers regarding the job competency performance of graduates. It is evident that graduates perceived excellent when conveying ideas clearly both orally and written in English, demonstrating the values of fairness, transparency, accountability, hard work, honesty, patience, diligence, innovativeness, and risk-taking, applying the principles of the different forms of communications, develop the ability to access, retrieve, and disseminate information using IT, perform quality work, develop a wholesome personality, and responsible citizenship, and participate in environmental scanning/awareness with the mean 3.30, 3.46, 3.31, 3.27, 3.50, 3.46, and 3.33, respectively. The mean scores for employers' perception of the graduate's performances for the same items are 2.86, 3.07, 3.00, 2.98, 3.14, 2.91, and 2.91, respectively. This comparison indicates that graduates' perception of performing excellently in those job competency constructs is not congruent with the assessment of employers asserting that graduates were just good performers and not excellent in their performance. However, there is

no significant difference in the perceptions of respondents in terms of conducting a feasibility study and other business research/plan and the awareness of the concepts, approaches, and techniques of environmental conservation, with a descriptive rating of “good,” showing that both respondents know that HRM graduates were not excellent in these activities.

Therefore, in job competency aspect, data indicate that employers perceived graduates as good performers while graduates perceived themselves as excellent. The difference in perception was initially observed in how they showcased their complete personality, displayed values and principles, and produced high-quality work. The disparity of viewpoints between the two respondents suggests that graduates were not wholly aligned with the company’s values and principles as evaluated by their employers. Embracing the core values and principles of the company is essential to the workers. Thus, graduates should learn to conform to the company’s attributes, making the employer satisfied with their performance. Secondly, regarding the use of information technology (IT), graduates are perceived to be excellent, while employers rated them as good. This finding was upsetting because technology is the industry’s demand in the 21st century. Hence, the academe should give importance to students’ digital literacy, especially, the online research skills, and should include in the curriculum of different programs at all courses [9], so that students can learn and practice their digital literacy abilities, which could make them confident and excellent performers in using IT. Research by Khan *et al.* [10] also suggested that through ICT or digital literacy, the critical skills, operational skills, visual learning style, collaborative learning style and learning system will be enhanced and the academic performance and employability will also be improved. On the other hand, study by Nikou *et al.* [11] underscored that supervisors or appointing officers in the industries should screen the level of digital literacy of their employees because this is an important skillset in the digital age. Thus, technological competencies should be addressed because this will increase their resilience, which would result in their concentration on their jobs and eventually cause them to perform better [12]. Hence, using IT during their academic years is an excellent strategy to make graduates competitive in the ever-changing environment where IT is thriving.

The third competency identified is the difference in respondents’ perception of the HRM graduates in conveying ideas, both orally and written in English, and applying the principles of the different forms of communication. The study of Wu *et al.* [13] highlighted that one of the important soft skills that affect the employability of graduates is communication skills, through verbal and non-verbal communication. In addition, English has become the global language used to acquire knowledge and meet the demands of the current job market [14]. The disparity of perception depicts that graduate were not fully competent in dealing with, discussing, and explaining to their employers, especially in English, which could lead to misunderstandings between both parties. Thus, for future graduates to become effective in expressing ideas and communicating, the academe should prepare students to practice in an English-speaking environment, engage in English in lessons, prepare authentic materials that encourage in-depth conversation, and use small class sizes to develop oral English skills as suggested by Karaca *et al.* [12].

Lastly, a significant difference in perception was observed in the company’s environmental scanning and knowledge of the country’s development. The employers rated the graduates as “good,” observing that these graduates were not fully adept in strategic planning and decision making, where managers need to be cognizant of the difficulties associated with environmental scanning that involve the organizations-environment interface from developed to emerging economies [15]. This suggests that graduates should engage themselves in the latest trends, issues, and situations of the business, economy, and country to participate in the top management’s strategic planning. Thus, in the teaching methodology and strategy, this study recommends that course subjects should have discussions on the up-to-date and real situations of the business world, and case study exercises, business plans, and the like should be interactive that soak the students with information or data about the situations in the business environment.

The graduates’ and employers’ perceptions of the career skills of the HRM graduates that are useful in the industry are shown in Table 5. The findings show that the graduate’s perception on their career skills, i.e., human relations/interpersonal skills ($z=3.577$, $p<.05$), communication skills ($z=4.755$, $p<.05$), information technology skills ($z=2.053$, $p<.05$), logical/critical thinking ($z=2.243$, $p<.05$), research skills ($z=2.962$, $p<.05$), leadership skills ($z=2.830$, $p<.05$), occupational/technical skills ($z=2.685$, $p<.05$), and exposure to local/international community within the field of specialization ($z=2.042$, $p<.05$) are significantly different from the employers perception, which implies that the employers assessment is not the same with the graduates perception. The plausible reason for these results could be that the HRM graduates’ performance did not attain the company’s career skills standard.

Furthermore, Table 5 shows a comparison of graduates’ and employers’ perceptions of the career skills of the graduates. Graduates perceived excellent in human relations/interpersonal skills, communication skills, information technology skills, logical/critical thinking, research skills, leadership/managerial skills, occupational/technical skills, and exposure to local/international community within the field of specialization with the mean 3.47, 3.50, 3.37, 3.32, 3.34, 3.36, 3.41, and 3.32 respectively. The mean scores for employers’

perception of the career skills performance of graduates for the same items are 2.95, 2.79, 3.02, 2.98, 2.86, 2.93, 3.00, and 2.98, respectively. It was noteworthy to determine that communication skills had the highest mean ($M=3.50$) among those constructs for the graduates; however, it had the lowest mean ($M=2.79$) for the employers. The next highest mean for the graduate's perception is human relations/interpersonal skills ($M=3.47$), followed by occupational/technical skills ($M=3.41$).

Table 4. Job competencies

No.	Job competencies	Graduate		Employer		Z-value	P-value
		Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1	Can convey ideas clearly both orally and written in English	3.30	Excellent	2.86	Good	3.40*	.00
2	Can prepare, analyze, and evaluate reports, proposals, and concept papers	3.26	Excellent	3.07	Good	1.31 ^{ns}	.19
3	Can demonstrate the values of fairness, transparency, accountability, hard work, honesty, patience, diligence, innovativeness, and risk-taking	3.46	Excellent	3.07	Good	2.23*	.03
4	Can apply the principles of the different forms of communications	3.31	Excellent	3.00	Good	2.06*	.04
5	Can develop the ability to access, retrieve, and disseminate information using IT	3.27	Excellent	2.98	Good	2.03*	.04
6	Can perform quality work	3.50	Excellent	3.14	Good	2.38*	.02
7	Able to understand the concept and principles of good interpersonal relations	3.41	Excellent	3.14	Good	1.87 ^{ns}	.06
8	Able to develop a wholesome personality	3.46	Excellent	2.91	Good	4.01*	.00
9	Can participate actively in business associations (meetings) and comply with policies and obligations	3.41	Excellent	3.16	Good	1.04 ^{ns}	.30
10	Able to demonstrate leadership qualities, civic-mindedness, and responsible citizenship	3.34	Excellent	3.07	Good	1.34 ^{ns}	.18
11	Able to participate in environmental scanning/awareness	3.33	Excellent	2.91	Good	2.91*	.00
12	Able to conduct a feasibility study and other business research/plan	3.18	Good	3.02	Good	1.06 ^{ns}	.29
13	Aware of the concepts, approaches, and techniques of environmental conservation	3.24	Good	2.98	Good	1.83 ^{ns}	.07

Note: descriptive interpretation (DI): 1.00 to 1.74=poor; 1.75 to 2.49=average; 2.50 to 3.24=good; 3.25 to 4.00=excellent

*=significant, ns=non-significant

On the other hand, the employer's second lowest perception is research skill ($M=2.86$) and leadership skill ($M=2.93$). Looking at the significant difference, the skills with the highest and lowest mean from the respondents also had the highest scores in the Z-value. In conclusion, the disparity of perception on the performance of skills such as communication, human relations/interpersonal, occupational/technical, research, and leadership skills can be a basis for the enhancement of the HRM curriculum so that students will develop those essential skills while studying and be competitive in performing their job when employed in a particular business firm after graduation.

In the aspect of career skills data showed that communication, human relations/interpersonal, occupational/technical, research, and leadership skills were identified to have a significant difference in the perception of the two respondents, where graduates rated them as excellent while employers rated them as good. These skills were critical in the industry and expected by the managers to be performed by their employees. Thus, the disparity shows that graduates did not meet employers' expectations when performing those skills. The same is true in the study of Karaca *et al.* [12] who concluded that there were still gaps in the skills and competencies of graduates from HEIs and the requirements of the industries in entry-level graduate positions. Communication skills were found to be the lowest score in the employers' perception, which was also associated with conveying ideas, both orally and written in English, and applying the principles of the different forms of communication in the job competencies constructs. The findings indicate that graduates were not excellent communicators as perceived by employers. This might be because communication skills cannot be learned and developed, unless there is adequate training, commitment and hard effort [16]. In fact, Hanapi and Nordin [17] revealed that the number one problem in the graduate's employability is communication skills, especially in English. Thus, the seriousness of research findings in communication skills should not be taken lightly. For instance, the study of Rautakoski *et al.* [18] discussed that low communication skill performance at an early age can delay the development of social-emotional competencies, which is a risk factor for developing social-emotional and behavioral problems. Communication is a vital skill in the business world. Besides, based on the study of competency hierarchy ranking for HRM, it was revealed that communication is the most required competency, followed by professional HR knowledge and usage of computer programs and digital tools [19]. In conclusion, academic institutions should focus on resolving the problem of low performance in communication skills to meet the

demands of the current job market [16], though becoming an effective communicator does not only rely on the academic environment or strategy.

A significant difference was also revealed in human relations or interpersonal skills. The gap shows that the graduates' high perception of their interpersonal relations is different from the assessment of their employers. Social exposure is a way to develop interpersonal skills. Thus, academic institutions should have a strategy or method of interpersonal relations to strengthen the knowledge of students on social interaction, especially interaction etiquette, and on understanding the importance of interpersonal interaction to personal growth and environmental adaptation [20]. Consequently, the gap should be considered when enhancing the students' skills because Hinchliffe and Jolly [6] stated that employers prefer those with good relations in and out of the organization, such as being cordial in dealing with colleagues and others and becoming ethical and professional. Indeed, human relations are essential in the workplace and business. In terms of occupational/technical skills, a gap was also identified, which suggests that graduate's lack of training in their field of specialization reflects their performance in their current job. Thus, academic institutions should design comprehensive training or immersion to enhance students' expertise in their specialization.

This teaching method or strategy is important since technical and business skills are significant skills needed for decision-making, problem-solving, and information analysis, as mentioned by Islam [21]. The disparity of perception in research skills is also alarming because research skills suggest critical thinking in analyzing and interpreting research data as the basis for making decisions and finding solutions to the problems encountered. This skill is the most challenging at the student level since writing a research paper is a struggle, particularly on integrating their knowledge in a research proposal [22]. To solve the lack of experience in doing research challenges, Ipanaqué-Zapata *et al.* [23] suggested that universities should form alliances with national and international institutions to strengthen the capacities of the teachers, researchers and students. On the other hand, the significance of technology and digital tools such as the digital open systems can contribute to improving and expanding opportunities in research, presentation of research results and image of the researcher and institution [24]. Thus, the use of the technology is very substantial in fostering research skills. The study also revealed the two respondents' different perceptions of leadership skills, which is disadvantageous to the organizations. Thus, business schools must engage their students in learning how to become leaders who can make organizations effective by making them more efficient, satisfying, equitable, and democratic [1].

Table 5. Career skills

No.	Career skills	Graduates		Employer		Z-value	P-value
		Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1	Human relations/interpersonal skills	3.47	Excellent	2.95	Good	3.58*	.00
2	Communication skills	3.50	Excellent	2.79	Good	4.75*	.00
3	Information technology skills	3.37	Excellent	3.02	Good	2.05*	.04
4	Logical/critical thinking	3.32	Excellent	2.98	Good	2.24*	.03
5	Entrepreneurial skills	3.29	Excellent	3.14	Good	.64 ^{ns}	.52
6	Problem-solving skills	3.35	Excellent	3.19	Good	.75 ^{ns}	.45
7	Presentation skills	3.40	Excellent	3.12	Good	1.88 ^{ns}	.06
8	Research skills	3.34	Excellent	2.86	Good	2.96*	.00
9	Leadership skills	3.36	Excellent	2.93	Good	2.83*	.01
10	Team spirit/people skill	3.45	Excellent	3.23	Good	1.01 ^{ns}	.31
11	Numerical/quantitative reasoning	3.31	Excellent	3.07	Good	1.20 ^{ns}	.23
12	Occupational/technical skills	3.41	Excellent	3.00	Good	2.69*	.01
13	Exposure to local/international community within the field of expertise	3.32	Excellent	2.98	Good	2.04*	.04

Note: descriptive interpretation (DI): 1.00 to 1.74=poor; 1.75 to 2.49=average; 2.50 to 3.24=good; 3.25 to 4.00=excellent
 *=significant, ns=non-significant

As shown in Table 6, there is a significant difference in the perception of the graduates and employers in the HRM graduate's team performance. It is noticeable that the significant difference in the perception of the graduates and their employers was portrayed when graduates were willing and able to work together rather than alone ($z=2.40$, $p<.05$), able to keep the team on track and help integrate the work performed by different members ($z=2.30$, $p<.05$), able to transmit information freely, efficiently and respectfully, and able to listen actively to coworkers ($z=4.08$, $p<.05$), and able to show empathy, provide emotional comfort, and build coworker feelings of confidence and self-worth, ($z=3.74$, $p<.05$). In contrast, there is no significant difference when graduates motivate team members to resolve disagreements. Table 6 also shows the graduates' perception of team performance with mean scores of 3.37, 3.35, 3.46, and 3.47, respectively, indicating that they perceived to be excellent team performers, while the employers' perception with mean scores of 3.00, 3.00, 2.88, and 2.93 respectively on the same items show that graduates were good

performers and not excellent when in a team. Thus, regarding team performance, the gap or mismatch shows that the employer's valuation differed from the graduates' perceptions. Academic institutions should not overlook this insight because 21st-century skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, communication, critical thinking, creative thinking, and ICT skills are prevailing.

Table 6. Performance in a team environment

No.	Team performance	Graduates		Employer		Z-value	P-value
		Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1	Willing and able to work together rather than alone	3.37	Excellent	3.00	Good	2.40*	.02
2	Able to keep the team on track and help integrate the work performed by different members.	3.35	Excellent	3.00	Good	2.30*	.02
3	Able to transmit information freely, efficiently, and respectfully, and able to listen actively to coworkers.	3.46	Excellent	2.88	Good	4.08*	.00
4	Able to show empathy, provide emotional comfort, and build coworker feelings of confidence and self-worth.	3.47	Excellent	2.93	Good	3.74*	.00
5	Able to motivate team members to resolve disagreements.	3.40	Excellent	3.14	Good	1.60 ^{ns}	.11

Note: descriptive interpretation (DI): 1.00 to 1.74=poor; 1.75 to 2.49=average; 2.50 to 3.24=good; 3.25 to 4.00=excellent
 *=significant, ns=non-significant

The significant gap in the performance of the graduates depicts that graduate did not meet their employers' expectations regarding their effectiveness in performing. Though they perceived excellence, their competitiveness is just good in the eyes of their employers, indicating that they need to work hard to become excellent performers. These findings instruct academic institutions to produce quality graduates who have aligned competencies with the industry. With this, the study of Odden [25] recommends that teachers produce content-rich and effective instructional practices that boost student learning to high levels, enhancing more skills and competencies needed by the industry. Moreover, learning methods through competency-based training can improve and develop the managerial and business competencies of the students and others' skills [26]. Also, Setyaningrum *et al.* [27] concluded that universities should enforce internships and more practical training to give students more exposure to actual work practice to improve the employability of graduates. Different methods and strategies can be designed to develop the student's competencies. Furthermore, academic institutions should always focus on developing students' potentials to becoming competitive as future professionals with the knowledge, attributes, and skills worthy of being employed in any industry. In a nutshell, researchers believe that a strong academe-industry partnership is very crucial and beneficial for curriculum enhancement. As such, collaboration and support from the academe and the industry in producing highly competent professionals can be one of the many strategies for addressing the discrepancy between the academe and the industry.

4. CONCLUSION

In pursuit of continuous development and improvement of the program offerings of every academic institution, academe, and industry must collaborate and focus on producing quality graduates that cater to the needs of the industry. Thus, this study examines the HRM graduate's job performance to assess the difference between their performance and the expectations of their employers, leading to curriculum revision and enhancement of the teaching methods and strategies. The research findings imply discrepancies in the respondents' perceptions regarding the job performance of HRM graduates. Significant differences in job competencies were explicitly found in values, personalities, quality of work, how graduates convey ideas, the use of IT, environmental scanning, and knowledge of the country's development. In terms of career skills, communication, human relations/interpersonal, occupational/technical, research, and leadership skills were identified to have a significant difference. Whereas, in team performance, both respondents identified the willingness to work, help others, transmit information, and show empathy, comfort, and self-worth as inconsistent. It is essential to consider the discrepancies between the graduates and employers to adjust the curriculum and close the gap between industry needs and graduates' abilities. In essence, this research can help academic institutions improve student performance by reviewing and revising its curriculum to ensure its relevance and responsiveness to the needs of the industry by applying relevant and innovative instructional materials, outcome-based and research-based activities, training, field exposure as additional methods and strategy to enhance the student's capabilities and team performance. A qualitative research approach may be considered for future research to analyze the in-depth findings and target the reason for the graduates' gap or mismatch performance.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that supports the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [DSP], upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Bratton and J. Gold, "Towards critical human resource management education (CHRME): a sociological imagination approach," *Work, Employment and Society*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 496–507, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1177/0950017014545266.
- [2] M. I. C. Celis, B. Festijo, and A. Cueto, "Graduate's employability: a tracer study for bachelor of science in hotel and restaurant management," *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*, vol. 1, no. 11, pp. 225–238, 2013.
- [3] J. T. Kwarteng and E. K. Mensah, "Employability of accounting graduates: analysis of skills sets," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 1–9, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09937.
- [4] C. K. Huang and C. Y. Lin, "Flipping business education: Transformative use of team-based learning in human resource management classrooms," *Educational Technology and Society*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 323–336, 2017.
- [5] W. Mainga, R. M. Daniel, and L. Alamil, "Perceptions of Employability Skills of Undergraduate Business Students in a Developing Country: An Exploratory Study," *Higher Learning Research Communications*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 28–63, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.18870/hlrc.2022.v12i1.1257.
- [6] G. W. Hinchliffe and A. Jolly, "Graduate identity and employability," *British Educational Research Journal*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 563–584, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1080/01411926.2010.482200.
- [7] J. Garbutt *et al.*, "Validating curricular competencies in innovation and entrepreneurship for biomedical research trainees: A modified Delphi approach," *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 165–183, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1017/cts.2019.390.
- [8] J. W. Creswell and J. D. Creswell, *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*, 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2017.
- [9] R. N. Indah, Toyyibah, A. S. Budhiningrum, and N. Afifi, "The Research Competence, Critical Thinking Skills and Digital Literacy of Indonesian EFL Students," *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 315–324, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.17507/jltr.1302.11.
- [10] N. Khan, A. Sarwar, T. B. Chen, and S. Khan, "Connecting digital literacy in higher education to the 21st century workforce," *Knowledge Management & E-Learning: An International Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 46, 2022, doi: 10.34105/j.kmel.2022.14.004.
- [11] S. Nikou, M. de Reuver, and M. M. Kanafi, "Workplace literacy skills—how information and digital literacy affect adoption of digital technology," *Journal of Documentation*, vol. 78, no. 7, pp. 371–391, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1108/JD-12-2021-0241.

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- [12] A. Karaca, M. E. Aydogmus, and N. Gunbas, "Enforced remote work during COVID-19 and the importance of technological competency: A job demands-resources perspective," *Revue Europeenne de Psychologie Appliquee*, vol. 73, no. 6, p. 100867, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.erap.2022.100867.
- [13] Y. Wu, L. Xu, and S. P. Philbin, "Evaluating the Role of the Communication Skills of Engineering Students on Employability According to the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) Theory," *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 12, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15129711.
- [14] P. M. I. Seraj, H. Habil, and M. K. Hasan, "Investigating the problems of teaching oral English communication skills in an EFL context at the tertiary level," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 501–516, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.29333/iji.2021.14228a.
- [15] B. P. Ebrahimi and O. O. Sawyerr, "Executive environmental scanning and strategic uncertainty: the impact of institutional context," in *Academy of Management Proceedings*, pp. 2151–6561, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.5465/ambpp.2016.16981abstract.
- [16] B. Sumaiya, S. Srivastava, V. Jain, and V. Prakash, "The Role of Effective Communication Skills in Professional Life," *World Journal of English Language*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 134–140, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.5430/wjel.v12n3p134.
- [17] Z. Hanapi and M. S. Nordin, "Unemployment among Malaysia graduates: graduates' attributes, lecturers' competency and quality of education," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 112, pp. 1056–1063, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1269.
- [18] P. Rautakoski, P. A. Ursin, A. S. Carter, A. Kaljonen, A. Nylund, and P. Pihlaja, "Communication skills predict social-emotional competencies," *Journal of communication disorders*, vol. 93, p. 106138, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jcomdis.2021.106138.
- [19] E. Bogdány, G. Cserhádi, and Á. Raffay-Danyi, "A proposed methodology for mapping and ranking competencies that HRM graduates need," *International Journal of Management Education*, vol. 21, no. 2, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100789.
- [20] J. Zhang, S. Zhao, H. Deng, C. Yuan, and Z. Yang, "Influence of interpersonal relationship on subjective well-being of college students: The mediating role of psychological capital," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 19, no. 9, p. e0293198, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0293198.
- [21] M. A. Islam, "Industry 4.0: Skill set for employability," *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 100280, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ssoho.2022.100280.
- [22] L. Maddens, F. Depaepe, A. Raes, and J. Elen, "Fostering students' motivation towards learning research skills: the role of autonomy, competence and relatedness support," *Instructional Science*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 165–199, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11251-022-09606-4.
- [23] M. Ipanaqué-Zapata, J. Figueroa-Quiñones, J. Bazalar-Palacios, W. Arhuis-Inca, M. Quiñones-Negrete, and D. Villarreal-Zegarra, "Research skills for university students' thesis in E-learning: Scale development and validation in Peru," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. e13770, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13770.
- [24] M. P. Leshchenko, A. M. Kolomiets, A. V. Iatsyshyn, V. V. Kovalenko, A. V. Dakal, and O. O. Radchenko, "Development of informational and research competence of postgraduate and doctoral students in conditions of digital transformation of science and education," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1840, no. 1, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1840/1/012057.
- [25] A. Odden, "Manage 'human capital' strategically," *Phi Delta Kappan*, vol. 92, no. 7, pp. 8–12, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1177/003172171109200703.
- [26] G. Ahmad, "Efforts in improving managerial competency of executing and supervisory position with competency based training method," *Ukrainian Journal of Educational Studies and Information Technology*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 29–43, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.32919/uesit.2020.02.03.
- [27] D. Setyaningrum, A. A. Hermawan, and D. Nastiti, "Assesing competency gaps of junior auditor: perception of employers, junior auditors, lecturers, and students," in *International Conference on Social Sciences and Information (SSR-SSI)*, pp. 1–9, 2019.

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